

Integrated Geotechnical Assessment of Subsurface Construction at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Northwestern Nigeria

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Abstract : This study presents an integrated geotechnical assessment of subsurface construction at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Northwestern Nigeria, to evaluate the suitability of the campus subsurface conditions for sustainable building development. An integrated approach involving field geological mapping, vertical electrical sounding (VES), and geotechnical laboratory testing was employed to characterize subsurface stratigraphy and assess the engineering properties of foundation materials. Twenty (20) VES stations were surveyed across the study area using the Advance Detector Model Technology Zone (ADMT ZN300) instrument to determine resistivity variations and delineate subsurface layers. The results revealed a three-to-four-layer geo-electric sequence comprising topsoil/lateritic overburden (0.5–6 m thick; 24–394 Ω m), weathered basement (8–15 m thick; 150–735 Ω m), fractured basement (200–750 Ω m), and fresh basement bedrock occurring at depths greater than 15 m with resistivity values of 750–1200 Ω m. Geotechnical analyses showed that the lateritic overburden exhibits variable engineering properties, with some locations characterized by low undrained shear strength ($c_u = 15\text{--}35$ kPa) and high compressibility, making them unsuitable for shallow foundations without ground improvement. In contrast, the fresh basement bedrock exhibits high bearing capacity (>500 kPa), indicating its suitability as a competent foundation horizon. Structural mapping of seventeen outcrops revealed an average dip of 19.2° and dominant NE–SE structural trends, which may

influence foundation orientation and groundwater flow. The study therefore recommends the use of deep foundation systems, such as pile or raft foundations extending to the fresh basement bedrock, particularly for multi-storey structures, alongside comprehensive site-specific geotechnical investigations before construction and avoidance of uncompacted lateritic clay zones. The findings provide essential baseline geotechnical and geophysical information for infrastructure planning and sustainable development at Federal University Gusau and other Basement Complex terrains in Northwestern Nigeria.

Keywords: Basement Complex; Geotechnical characterization; Subsurface stratigraphy; Foundation engineering; Electrical resistivity; Federal University Gusau; Building construction;

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1.0 Introduction

Building failures associated with inadequate subsurface investigations remain one of the major engineering challenges worldwide, particularly in developing countries where rapid urbanization often exceeds the pace of comprehensive geotechnical site investigations. Inadequate characterization of subsurface conditions frequently results in excessive settlement, structural distress, foundation failure, increased maintenance costs, and substantial economic losses (Anukwu & Obi, 2026).. Consequently, detailed geological and geotechnical investigations have become indispensable for sustainable infrastructure development and modern foundation engineering. Geological and geotechnical site characterization forms the foundation of safe, economical, and sustainable civil engineering practice by providing essential information on soil stratification, rock competence, groundwater conditions, and geological structures that directly influence foundation design and long-term structural performance. This process involves the systematic investigation of subsurface conditions to gather critical data on soil and rock properties, groundwater regimes, and geological structures that may influence

foundation performance and structural stability (Omolaiye *et al.*, 2024; Ameh *et al.*, 2025). Such investigations typically encompass field geological mapping, geophysical surveys, borehole drilling, and laboratory testing of soil and rock samples to determine engineering parameters essential for modern foundation design. The rapid expansion of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, particularly in the northwestern region, has necessitated accelerated infrastructure development to accommodate growing student populations and academic programs. Federal University Gusau (FUGUS), established in 2013 in Zamfara State, is experiencing significant campus development requiring rigorous subsurface evaluation to mitigate structural failures and ensure long-term building performance. Construction within the Nigerian Basement Complex terrain presents unique geotechnical challenges due to heterogeneous weathering profiles, variable rock competence, differential settlement potential, and the presence of problematic clay minerals that can compromise foundation integrity (Adamu *et al.*, 2024; Irunkwor *et al.*, 2025). The complex tropical weathering processes characteristic of the Nigerian Basement Complex produce highly variable subsurface conditions over relatively short distances, making generalized foundation designs unreliable. Therefore, site-specific geological and geotechnical investigations are essential for minimizing engineering uncertainties and optimizing foundation selection.

Several studies across Nigeria have demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating geological mapping, geophysical surveys, and laboratory geotechnical testing for engineering site investigations. Electrical resistivity techniques have been widely used to delineate subsurface weathering profiles, identify competent foundation horizons, detect fracture zones, and evaluate groundwater conditions,

while laboratory geotechnical testing provides quantitative information on soil strength, compressibility, plasticity, and bearing capacity. (Alabi *et al.*, 2024; Falade *et al.*, 2025). Despite these advances, previous investigations have primarily focused on highways, residential developments, dams, and urban engineering projects, while relatively few studies have addressed integrated geological and geotechnical characterization for rapidly expanding university campuses located within the Northwestern Nigerian Basement Complex. Furthermore, no comprehensive investigation has combined geological mapping, structural analysis, electrical resistivity surveying, and laboratory geotechnical testing to evaluate foundation conditions across the Federal University Gusau campus. This lack of site-specific subsurface information limits the reliability of foundation design and increases the potential for structural distress and costly engineering failures. This knowledge gap poses significant risks for infrastructure development, as inappropriate foundation design without adequate subsurface information can lead to structural distress, excessive settlement, and premature building failure. Geotechnical investigations for construction purposes involve systematic site examination by qualified geologists and engineers who document surface geology, collect representative soil and rock samples, measure structural features, and conduct in-situ and laboratory tests to determine engineering properties. The resulting data are integrated into geological and geotechnical models that illustrate the spatial distribution of foundation materials, structural elements, and potential geohazards—information critical for informed decision-making in construction planning and design (Omolaiye *et al.*, 2024; Ameh *et al.*, 2025). An integrated geological, geophysical, and geotechnical approach provides a more reliable characterization of

subsurface conditions than any single investigation method used independently. Geological mapping identifies lithological units and structural discontinuities, geophysical techniques provide continuous imaging of subsurface stratigraphy over large areas, and laboratory geotechnical testing supplies quantitative measurements of engineering properties. The integration of these complementary techniques significantly improves the accuracy of subsurface models and enhances the reliability of foundation design.

Against this background, this study aims to conduct an integrated geological, geophysical, and geotechnical assessment of the Federal University Gusau campus to evaluate the suitability of subsurface materials for building foundation construction. Specifically, the study documents the geological and structural characteristics of the area, delineates subsurface stratigraphy using electrical resistivity techniques, determines the engineering properties of foundation materials through laboratory testing, evaluates their suitability for shallow and deep foundation systems, and develops practical recommendations for sustainable infrastructure development.

The findings of this study will provide a comprehensive geotechnical database for future infrastructure development at Federal University Gusau, improve the reliability of foundation design, reduce construction-related risks, minimize long-term maintenance costs, and contribute to engineering knowledge on integrated subsurface characterization within the Nigerian Basement Complex. The results will also serve as a valuable reference for infrastructure planning in similar crystalline basement terrains across Northwestern Nigeria.

1.1 Literature Review

1.1.1 Foundation Systems and Engineering Characteristics

The choice of foundation type depends primarily on the engineering properties of the subsurface materials, anticipated structural loads, and groundwater conditions. Foundations are generally classified into shallow and deep foundation systems based on their depth of embedment and mechanism of load transfer.

Shallow foundations, commonly referred to as spread footings, transfer structural loads to competent near-surface soils and include isolated footings, strip footings, combined footings, and raft (mat) foundations. These systems are economical, relatively easy to construct, and are suitable where competent bearing strata occur within shallow depths. In Basement Complex terrains, shallow foundations are generally appropriate where fresh bedrock occurs within approximately 1.5–3.0 m of the ground surface or where well-compacted lateritic materials possess adequate bearing capacity and low compressibility.

Where near-surface soils exhibit poor engineering characteristics or thick weathered profiles are present, deep foundations become necessary. Deep foundations, including driven piles, bored piles, drilled shafts, and caissons, transfer structural loads to deeper competent strata. In the Nigerian Basement Complex, pile foundations socketed into fresh basement bedrock are frequently adopted for multi-storey buildings and heavily loaded structures because they provide higher bearing capacity and minimize differential settlement, although they require specialized construction equipment and higher installation costs.

The engineering behaviour of foundation materials within the Nigerian Basement Complex is strongly influenced by weathering processes. A typical weathering profile consists of topsoil, lateritic clay or laterite, weathered basement (saprolite), fractured basement, and fresh basement bedrock. The thickness and engineering properties of these

layers vary considerably depending on lithology, tectonic structures, drainage conditions, and climatic influences. Lateritic soils commonly exhibit high plasticity, significant swell–shrink potential, relatively low shear strength, and moderate to high compressibility, thereby requiring detailed evaluation before foundation construction. In contrast, fresh granitic, gneissic, and migmatitic basement rocks generally provide excellent bearing capacity and low compressibility, although their engineering performance may be influenced by joints, fractures, and weathering intensity.

Groundwater conditions also exert considerable influence on foundation performance. Within Basement Complex terrains, groundwater commonly occurs under unconfined conditions within the weathered overburden and under semi-confined to confined conditions within fractured basement rocks. Seasonal fluctuations in groundwater levels, typically ranging from 1.5 to 15 m below ground surface in Northwestern Nigeria, may reduce bearing capacity, destabilize excavations, induce buoyancy forces on underground structures, and necessitate dewatering during construction. Furthermore, groundwater chemistry may adversely affect reinforced concrete through sulfate attack or chloride-induced corrosion. Consequently, hydrogeological investigations should be integrated with geotechnical site investigations to ensure safe and economical foundation design.

The engineering properties of the principal foundation materials also vary considerably with weathering grade. Well-laterized soils generally exhibit liquid limits of 30–60%, plasticity indices of 10–30%, undrained shear strengths of 15–50 kPa, compression indices of 0.15–0.45, maximum dry densities between 1.6 and 2.0 Mg/m³, and optimum moisture contents of approximately 10–20%. Weathered basement materials typically

possess moisture contents of 10–30%, unconfined compressive strengths of 0.5–5 MPa, deformability moduli of 50–500 MPa, and permeabilities ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} m/s depending on fracture density. Fresh basement rocks exhibit considerably superior engineering properties, including unconfined compressive strengths of 50–250 MPa, Young's modulus values of 20–70 GPa, Poisson's ratios of 0.15–0.30, and bulk densities between 2.6 and 2.8 Mg/m³, making them the preferred foundation horizon for heavy engineering structures.

1.1.2 Study Area

Federal University Gusau is located in Gusau, the capital of Zamfara State in Northwestern Nigeria, between latitudes 12°05'N and 12°10'N and longitudes 06°43'E and 06°48'E (Fig. 1). The university occupies approximately 2,500 hectares and is bounded by residential developments to the north,

agricultural land to the south and east, and the Gusau–Sokoto Highway to the west.

The study area is characterized by gently undulating plains with elevations ranging between 350 and 450 m above mean sea level. The terrain comprises scattered granitic inselbergs, shallow valleys, and seasonal drainage channels flowing southwards toward the Rima River Basin. The climate is tropical semi-arid, characterized by a wet season extending from May to September with average annual rainfall of 800–1000 mm and a prolonged dry season from October to April dominated by Harmattan winds. Vegetation is typical Sudan Savanna, consisting mainly of scattered Acacia, Baobab, and Neem trees with seasonal grasses. The predominant soils are tropical ferruginous laterites and lateritic clays derived from in-situ weathering of the underlying crystalline basement rocks.

Fig. 1. Topographic map of the Federal University Gusau study area

1.1.3 Geological Setting

Federal University Gusau is situated within the Precambrian Basement Complex of Northwestern Nigeria, which forms part of the Pan-African orogenic belt that experienced extensive tectonothermal reworking approximately 600 ± 150 Ma. The Nigerian Basement Complex comprises three principal lithotectonic units: the Migmatite–Gneiss Complex, the Schist Belts, and the syn- to post-tectonic Older Granites.

The study area lies within the Older Granite province of the Northwestern Nigerian Massif and is predominantly underlain by coarse-grained to porphyritic granitic intrusions with localized occurrences of migmatitic gneisses and narrow schist belts. These granitic bodies were emplaced during the late stages of the Pan-African orogeny and subsequently modified by prolonged weathering, erosion, and multiple phases of tectonic deformation.

Structural features within the area are dominated by NE–SW to NNE–SSW trending foliation planes, joints, faults, mineral lineations, and quartz–aplite veins that reflect regional Pan-African deformation. Weathering intensity varies considerably across the area, producing residual regolith profiles between approximately 5 and 25 m thick, with thicker weathered materials generally occurring within topographic depressions and poorly drained areas.

The geological evolution of the area involved the deposition of sedimentary and volcanic protoliths, regional metamorphism during the Eburnean Orogeny, widespread Pan-African granitic magmatism and deformation, prolonged uplift and erosion throughout the Paleozoic and Mesozoic eras, and intense tropical weathering during the Cenozoic that resulted in extensive laterite development. These geological processes have produced highly heterogeneous subsurface conditions that significantly influence the engineering behaviour of foundation materials and

underscore the need for detailed geological and geotechnical investigations before infrastructure development.

Federal University Gusau is situated within the Precambrian Basement Complex of Northwestern Nigeria, a major geological province that forms part of the Pan-African mobile belt and experienced extensive tectonothermal reworking during the Pan-African Orogeny approximately 600 ± 150 Ma (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2025a). The Nigerian Basement Complex is conventionally subdivided into three principal lithotectonic units: the Migmatite–Gneiss Complex, representing the oldest high-grade metamorphic basement rocks; the Schist Belts, composed predominantly of metasedimentary and metavolcanic rocks; and the syn- to post-tectonic Older Granites, which intruded the earlier basement assemblages during the late stages of the Pan-African orogenic event (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2025b). The study area lies within the Older Granite province of the Northwestern Nigerian Massif, where the bedrock is dominated by coarse-grained to porphyritic granitic intrusions with localized occurrences of migmatitic gneisses and narrow schistose belts. Regional geological studies indicate that these granitic bodies were emplaced during the terminal stages of the Pan-African orogeny and subsequently modified by prolonged subaerial weathering, erosional unroofing, and multiple phases of tectonic deformation (Lawal *et al.*, 2025). Structurally, the area is characterized by dominant NE–SW to NNE–SSW trends expressed by foliation planes, mineral lineations, joints, faults, and quartz–aplite veins that reflect the regional Pan-African deformation pattern (Suleiman & Bello, 2024). Field observations further reveal evidence of brittle deformation, including fractured rock masses, fault breccias, shear zones, and extensive quartz–aplite vein networks. These structural discontinuities significantly

influence groundwater occurrence, weathering patterns, and the engineering behaviour of foundation materials within the study area. Weathering within the area is spatially variable, producing residual regolith profiles ranging from approximately 5 to 25 m in thickness. Thicker weathered profiles generally occur in topographic depressions and poorly drained areas, whereas relatively thin overburden is developed over elevated granitic outcrops. This variation in weathering intensity gives rise to heterogeneous subsurface conditions characterized by alternating layers of lateritic soils, saprolite, fractured basement, and competent fresh basement rock, which exert significant control on the geotechnical properties of the subsurface materials.

The geological evolution of the study area reflects a complex, multiphase tectonic history. This evolution involved the deposition of sedimentary and volcanic protoliths within ancient marginal basin environments, followed by regional metamorphism and deformation during the Eburnean Orogeny (approximately 2000 Ma). Subsequent Pan-African tectonothermal activity

(approximately 600 Ma) was accompanied by widespread granitic magmatism, high-grade metamorphism, and regional deformation, culminating in the emplacement of the Older Granites. Following these tectonic events, prolonged continental uplift, peneplanation during the Paleozoic–Mesozoic transition, and intense tropical weathering under humid Cenozoic climatic conditions resulted in extensive laterite development and the formation of thick weathering profiles that characterize much of the present-day landscape (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2025b). The combined effects of lithological variability, structural deformation, and differential weathering have produced complex subsurface conditions that strongly influence foundation competence, groundwater distribution, and engineering performance. Consequently, comprehensive geological, geophysical, and geotechnical investigations are essential for the proper characterization of foundation materials and the sustainable planning and design of engineering infrastructure within the Federal University Gusau campus.

Fig. 2. DEM Map of Federal University (Source: Saidu Abdullahi 202)

2.0 *Materials and Methods*

2.1 *Research Design and Field Investigation*

This study employed an integrated geological, geophysical, and geotechnical approach to characterize the subsurface conditions of the Federal University Gusau campus and evaluate their suitability for building foundation construction. The methodology combined detailed field geological mapping, electrical resistivity surveying, and laboratory geotechnical testing to provide comprehensive information on lithology, structural characteristics, subsurface stratigraphy, and the engineering properties of foundation materials.

Field geological investigations were carried out across the study area using standard geological mapping and compass-traverse techniques. A total of seventeen (17) rock outcrops were identified, described, and mapped to determine the lithological composition, weathering characteristics, structural features, and spatial distribution of the bedrock units. Structural measurements, including the strike and dip of foliations, joints, fractures, and quartz veins, were recorded using a Brunton compass. Representative soil and rock samples were collected from selected outcrops and trial pits for laboratory analyses, while the geographic coordinates and elevations of observation points were determined using a handheld Global Positioning System (GPS).

2.2 *Geophysical Investigation*

Subsurface characterization was undertaken using the Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) technique with the Schlumberger electrode configuration to determine the resistivity distribution and infer the subsurface lithological sequence. Twenty (20) VES stations were established along six traverses (Profiles A–F) with station spacing ranging from 200 to 500 m to ensure adequate spatial coverage of the study area (Fig. 3). Data acquisition was carried out using an ADMT

ZN300 Digital Resistivity Meter operating in the Schlumberger array configuration. The maximum current electrode half-spacing ($AB/2$) was 100 m, while the potential electrode half-spacing ($MN/2$) varied incrementally from 0.5 to 20 m, providing an estimated investigation depth of approximately 80–120 m.

The VES stations were strategically selected to represent different geological conditions and proposed construction locations within the university campus. During data acquisition, electrodes were installed along straight traverses with appropriate spacing to minimize contact resistance and improve data quality. Apparent resistivity measurements were acquired at successive electrode separations, and repeated observations were made where necessary to ensure data consistency and reproducibility. Geographic coordinates and elevations were recorded for all VES stations using a handheld GPS receiver.

The field resistivity data were processed and interpreted using IPI2Win software to obtain one-dimensional resistivity-depth models. The interpreted geoelectric sections were subsequently correlated with geological field observations and available borehole information to establish the subsurface lithological sequence. Based on the interpreted resistivity values, the subsurface materials were classified into topsoil/laterite (20–400 Ωm), weathered basement (100–750 Ωm), fractured basement (200–800 Ωm), and fresh basement bedrock (>750 Ωm).

2.3 *Geotechnical Laboratory Investigation and Engineering Assessment*

Representative soil and rock samples collected during the field investigations were analysed in the Geotechnical Laboratory of the Federal University Gusau following the procedures specified in the Nigerian Standard Specifications as well as relevant ASTM and BS 1377 standards. Laboratory testing of soil samples included grain-size distribution using

sieve and hydrometer analyses, determination of Atterberg limits (liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index), natural moisture content by the oven-drying method, Standard Proctor compaction tests, California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests under soaked and unsoaked conditions, unconfined compression and direct shear tests for shear strength determination, and one-dimensional consolidation (oedometer) tests for evaluating compressibility and settlement characteristics. Rock samples were tested to determine their engineering properties through unconfined compressive strength (UCS) testing, point load index determination, slake durability testing to evaluate resistance to weathering, and measurements of bulk density and porosity using the saturation and buoyancy methods.

The geological, geophysical, and laboratory results were integrated to assess the engineering suitability of the identified subsurface materials for foundation construction. The assessment focused on evaluating the bearing capacity of the different geological units, estimating the settlement potential of compressible layers, determining the suitability of the subsurface materials for shallow and deep foundation systems, assessing groundwater conditions and drainage requirements, and evaluating the availability and engineering quality of naturally occurring construction materials within the study area.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Geological Mapping and Structural Characteristics

Field geological mapping identified seventeen (17) rock outcrops distributed across the Federal University Gusau campus. The spatial distribution of these outcrops and the mapped lithological units are presented in Fig. 3. The study area is underlain predominantly by Older Granites of the Nigerian Basement Complex, with lithological variations ranging

from fine-grained granites to coarse porphyritic granites. Three principal geomorphological expressions were recognized during field investigations, namely low-lying ridges, river-channel exposures, and whale-back granitic outcrops.

The low-lying ridges consist mainly of moderately weathered granites exhibiting well-developed joint systems, while the river-channel exposures reveal fresh to slightly weathered granites with minimal overburden development. The whale-back outcrops comprise massive dome-shaped granitic bodies characterized by prominent exfoliation joints, indicating prolonged physical weathering. These fresh granitic exposures provide direct evidence of competent basement rock occurring at shallow depths in several parts of the study area.

Structural measurements obtained from the seventeen outcrops indicate that the dominant structural trends are oriented in the NE–SE to NNE–SSW directions, with an average dip of 19.2°. These orientations correspond closely with the regional Pan-African structural fabric previously reported for the Nigerian Basement Complex. The presence of foliations, joints, fractures, and quartz veins suggests that the area has undergone multiple phases of tectonic deformation, producing discontinuities that influence groundwater movement, weathering intensity, and rock mass strength.

Fig. 3 therefore demonstrates that the geology of the study area is highly heterogeneous, with variable degrees of weathering and structural deformation across the campus.

Such variability is expected to influence the engineering behaviour of foundation materials and justifies the need for integrated geological, geophysical, and geotechnical investigations before construction.

Engineering implication. Fresh granite exposed at shallow depth provides highly competent foundation materials suitable for heavy structures, whereas weathered and

fractured zones may experience reduced bearing capacity and increased differential settlement if not properly investigated.

3.2 Geoelectrical Characterization of the Subsurface

The interpreted Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) results indicate that the subsurface beneath the Federal University Gusau campus consists predominantly of three to four geo-

electric layers. Representative sounding curves and interpreted layer parameters are presented in Table 1, while the generalized geo-electric characteristics of all sounding stations are summarized in Table 2. The spatial distribution of the VES stations is illustrated in Fig. 4, and representative interpreted sounding curves generated using IPI2Win software are presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 3. Geological map of Federal University Gusau campus showing lithological units, outcrop locations. (Source: Saidu Abdullahi 2026)

Table 1: Summary of VES Curve Types and Layer Characteristics (Source: Field Data)

VES Point	Curve Type	Layer (Topsoil)	1 Layer (Weathered)	2 Layer (Fractured)	3 Layer (Fresh)	4
VES 1	H	2.1 m / 145 Ωm	12.5 m / 380 Ωm	-	>15 m / 890 Ωm	
VES 2	K	1.8 m / 210 Ωm	8.3 m / 520 Ωm	18.7 m / 680 Ωm	>30 m / 1050 Ωm	
VES 3	H	3.2 m / 98 Ωm	15.1 m / 290 Ωm	-	>20 m / 820 Ωm	
VES 4	HK	1.5 m / 175 Ωm	6.8 m / 410 Ωm	12.3 m / 590 Ωm	>25 m / 950 Ωm	
VES 5	H	2.8 m / 132 Ωm	11.4 m / 340 Ωm	-	>18 m / 870 Ωm	

Table 2: Geo-electric Layer Parameters for All VES Stations (Source: Field Data)

Layer	Lithological Interpretation	Resistivity Range (Ωm)	Thickness Range (m)	Average Thickness (m)	Engineering Significance
1	Topsoil/Laterite/Lateritic Clay	24–394	0.5–6.0	2.3	Variable competence; clay-rich zones prone to swelling
2	Weathered Basement (Saprolite)	150–735	5.0–18.5	10.8	Moderate bearing capacity; fracture-dependent permeability
3	Fractured Basement	200–750	0–25.0	8.5	Potential aquifer; requires grouting for foundation support
4	Fresh Basement Bedrock	750–1200	∞ (to - depth)	-	High competence; optimal foundation bearing stratum

Fig. 4. Topographic map of Federal University Gusau showing VES Point (Source: Saidu Abdullahi 2026)

The representative VES models presented in Table 1 show considerable lateral variation in both resistivity and layer thickness. Topsoil resistivity ranges from 98 to 210 Ωm , with thicknesses between 1.5 and 3.2 m, indicating variations in moisture content and clay composition. The weathered basement exhibits resistivity values ranging from 290 to 520 Ωm and thicknesses between 6.8 and 15.1 m, suggesting variable degrees of weathering across the study area. Fresh basement resistivity exceeds 820 Ωm at all representative stations and reaches 1050 Ωm at VES 2, confirming the presence of competent crystalline basement at depth.

The comprehensive interpretation summarized in Table 2 indicates that the first geo-electric layer comprises topsoil, laterite, and lateritic clay with resistivity values ranging from 24 to 394 Ωm and thicknesses between 0.5 and 6.0 m, averaging 2.3 m. These low-to-moderate resistivity values are typical of clay-rich lateritic materials containing variable moisture contents. From an engineering perspective, this layer exhibits highly variable competence, and clay-rich zones are susceptible to swelling and shrinkage, making them unsuitable as direct foundation materials without treatment.

The second layer corresponds to weathered basement (saprolite), characterized by resistivity values of 150–735 Ωm and thicknesses ranging from 5.0 to 18.5 m, with an average thickness of 10.8 m. This layer constitutes the principal weathering horizon beneath much of the campus and exhibits moderate bearing capacity. However, its engineering behaviour depends strongly on weathering intensity and fracture density.

The third layer represents fractured basement with resistivity values between 200 and 750 Ωm and thicknesses reaching 25 m in some locations. The occurrence of fractured basement indicates structurally controlled weathering and suggests the presence of secondary groundwater reservoirs. Although

fractured basement may possess moderate strength, extensive fracturing can reduce rock mass competence and may require pressure grouting or other ground improvement measures before foundation construction.

Fresh basement bedrock forms the fourth geo-electric layer and exhibits resistivity values ranging from 750 to 1200 Ωm . This layer extends beyond the maximum depth of investigation and represents the most competent engineering horizon within the study area. The high resistivity values reflect fresh crystalline granite with minimal weathering and excellent load-bearing characteristics. The interpreted VES curve types further reveal that H-type curves constitute 45% (9 stations) of the survey, K-type curves account for 35% (7 stations), while HK-type curves represent 20% (4 stations). The predominance of H-type curves indicates widespread development of thick weathered horizons containing relatively conductive materials, particularly within topographic depressions where clay accumulation and groundwater saturation are greater. Conversely, K-type curves are more common on elevated terrain where thinner weathered profiles overlie competent basement rocks. The HK-type responses indicate complex four-layer subsurface conditions involving fractured basement horizons.

These geophysical results confirm significant spatial variability in weathering depth and basement topography throughout the study area. The interpreted VES curves comprise three principal curve types (Fig. 5). H-type curves ($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3$) constitute 45% (9 stations) of the sounding locations and are characterized by a relatively conductive intermediate layer underlying a more resistive topsoil. This response indicates the presence of thick weathered zones with relatively low resistivity resulting from increased clay content and moisture saturation. These curve

types occur predominantly within topographic depressions where weathering is more advanced. K-type curves ($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3$) account for 35% (7 stations) and are typical of ridge crests and well-drained areas where relatively competent weathered basement or thin overburden overlies fresh basement rock. HK-type curves, representing 20% (4 stations), indicate more complex four-layer subsurface conditions involving weathered and fractured basement horizons. The occurrence of these curve types confirms the heterogeneous nature of the subsurface across the study area and demonstrates significant lateral variation in weathering intensity and basement topography. A consideration of engineering implication indicated that areas characterized by thin overburden and shallow competent basement are suitable for shallow spread foundations, whereas locations underlain by thick weathered profiles and fractured basement will require raft or deep foundation systems to minimize excessive settlement. The engineering properties of the major overburden materials are summarized in Table 3. Three principal engineering soil units were identified: lateritic clay, lateritic gravel, and weathered granite saprolite.

Lateritic clay contains 25–40% clay, exhibits liquid limits between 35 and 55%, plasticity indices ranging from 15 to 28%, and is classified as CL–CH under the Unified Soil Classification System. These materials exhibit maximum dry densities of 1.62–1.78 Mg/m³, optimum moisture contents between 14 and 22%, soaked CBR values of 8–25%, undrained cohesion values of 15–35 kPa, and compression indices ranging from 0.25 to 0.45. These characteristics indicate moderate to high compressibility and relatively low shear strength, making untreated lateritic clay unsuitable for supporting heavily loaded foundations.

In contrast, lateritic gravel is essentially non-plastic and contains 45–65% gravel,

producing significantly higher compaction characteristics and soaked CBR values ranging from 35 to 65%. These materials exhibit friction angles of 32–38°, indicating excellent shear resistance and making them suitable for pavement subgrades and engineered fill after proper compaction. Engineering implication. Fresh granite exposed at shallow depth provides highly competent foundation materials suitable for heavy structures, whereas weathered and fractured zones may experience reduced bearing capacity and increased differential settlement if not properly investigated.

Weathered granite saprolite exhibits intermediate engineering properties with maximum dry densities ranging from 1.75 to 1.92 Mg/m³, soaked CBR values between 15 and 35%, cohesion values of 25–65 kPa, and friction angles between 22 and 32°. Although these materials possess greater strength than lateritic clay, their engineering performance varies considerably depending on weathering intensity and moisture conditions.

Overall, the laboratory results demonstrate that engineering properties vary substantially across the study area owing to differences in lithology, weathering, and clay mineral content.

Engineering implication. Lateritic gravel provides the most suitable natural construction material within the study area, whereas clay-rich lateritic soils require stabilization, replacement, or deep foundation support before engineering use.

3.4 Integrated Subsurface Stratigraphy and Engineering Assessment

Engineering implication. Fresh granite exposed at shallow depth provides highly competent foundation materials suitable for heavy structures, whereas weathered and fractured zones may experience reduced bearing capacity and increased differential settlement if not properly investigated.

Engineering implication. Fresh granite exposed at shallow depth provides highly competent foundation materials suitable for heavy structures, whereas weathered and fractured zones may experience reduced bearing capacity and increased differential settlement if not properly investigated.

Integration of the geological mapping, VES interpretation, and laboratory testing enabled the development of a generalized subsurface model for the Federal University Gusau campus (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) curves for Location 1-6 obtained using IPI2WIN software

The first layer consists of topsoil and lateritic overburden with thicknesses ranging from 0.5 to 6.0 m. This layer comprises organic topsoil, lateritic clay, and lateritic gravel and exhibits highly variable engineering properties. Clay-rich portions possess low shear strength and relatively high compressibility, making them unsuitable as direct foundation materials without excavation or stabilization. The second layer consists of weathered basement (saprolite), which occurs at depths

between 5 and 20 m and averages 10.8 m in thickness. Resistivity values range from 150 to 735 Ω m, while estimated allowable bearing capacities range between 100 and 250 kPa. These materials may adequately support lightly loaded structures using raft foundations, provided detailed settlement analyses are undertaken. The third layer comprises fractured basement exhibiting resistivity values between 200 and 750 Ω m. Although this horizon may function

as a productive groundwater reservoir, fracture development reduces rock mass strength and may necessitate grouting or other ground improvement measures where heavily loaded structures are proposed. Fresh basement bedrock forms the fourth engineering layer and occurs generally below 15 m depth with resistivity values ranging from 750 to 1200 Ωm . This horizon possesses estimated bearing capacities exceeding 500 kPa, making it the preferred foundation level for multi-storey buildings and other heavily loaded infrastructure.

The integrated results demonstrate that subsurface conditions beneath the Federal University Gusau campus are highly variable both laterally and vertically. Consequently, no single foundation solution is appropriate for the entire campus. Foundation selection should therefore be based on detailed site-specific investigations incorporating geological mapping, electrical resistivity surveys, and geotechnical laboratory testing.

The observed weathering profile thickness of 5–25 m agrees well with values reported for other Basement Complex terrains in Nigeria by Olorunfemi and Olorunfemi (1987) and Dan-Hassan and Olorunfemi (1999). Likewise, the high plasticity and compressibility of the lateritic clays are consistent with previous studies on tropical lateritic soils reported by Jones (1985) and Clark (1985). The high competence of the fresh basement bedrock also agrees with the engineering characteristics of Nigerian Older Granites reported by Wright (1992) and Acworth (1987).

Overall, the integrated geological, geophysical, and geotechnical investigation provides a robust basis for foundation design and significantly reduces the uncertainty associated with infrastructure development within the Federal University Gusau campus and similar Basement Complex terrains in Northwestern Nigeria.

4.0 Conclusion

This study integrated geological mapping, Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES), and geotechnical laboratory testing to evaluate the suitability of subsurface conditions for foundation construction at Federal University Gusau. The results indicate that the study area is underlain by Older Granites of the Nigerian Basement Complex, with a heterogeneous weathering profile consisting of lateritic overburden (0.5–6.0 m), weathered basement (5.0–18.5 m), fractured basement, and competent fresh basement generally occurring below 15 m depth. Geophysical investigations identified three to four geo-electric layers with resistivity values of 24–394 Ωm , 150–735 Ωm , 200–750 Ωm , and 750–1200 Ωm , corresponding to the topsoil, weathered basement, fractured basement, and fresh basement, respectively. Geotechnical results show that lateritic clay possesses low shear strength (15–35 kPa) and high compressibility ($C_c = 0.25\text{--}0.45$), making it unsuitable for shallow foundations without improvement, whereas the fresh basement provides high bearing capacity (>500 kPa) and is the most suitable foundation horizon. The pronounced lateral variability in subsurface conditions highlights the need for site-specific foundation design. Accordingly, all future developments should be preceded by comprehensive geotechnical investigations combining geophysical surveys with boreholes and laboratory testing. Shallow foundations should only be adopted where competent bedrock occurs at shallow depth after appropriate ground improvement, while medium- and high-rise buildings should be supported on piles socketed into fresh basement bedrock. Proper compaction of engineered fill, adequate drainage, and post-construction settlement monitoring are also recommended to ensure safe and sustainable infrastructure development. Future studies should employ advanced three-dimensional

geophysical imaging and long-term groundwater monitoring to further improve foundation design within the Basement Complex terrain.

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Declaration

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Not applicable

Consent for Publication

All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript and consented to its publication.

Availability of Data and Materials

Data shall be made available upon request

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

Authors' Contributions

Saidu Abdullahi conceived the study, conducted field investigations, analysed data, and drafted the manuscript. Ahmad Abdullaziz and Abdul'aziz Bello participated in geological mapping, geophysical surveys, laboratory analyses, and data interpretation. Ismail Abdulrahman contributed to field sampling, laboratory testing, and manuscript revision. Sufiyanu A. Sani supervised the research, validated the results, critically revised the manuscript, and approved the final version.

